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The Mediating Effect of Time Management on the Relationship Between Work Ethics and Professionalism Among Public School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this study was to look at the role that time management had in mediating the relationship between work ethics and professionalism among 310 teachers in the Magsaysay South and North District of the Division of Davao del Sur. The descriptive correlation technique was used in this study's non-experimental design. This statistical tools used were mean, Pearson r , and path analysis using AMOS. Research instruments on time management, work ethics and professionalism which were validated were used as sources of data. Results showed that the level of work ethics of teachers is generally described as high. Similarly, their level of professionalism indicated a high rating. Likewise, their level of time management is mostly high. Using Pearson r , the results revealed that there are significant relationships between work ethics and time management, time management and professionalism, and work ethics and professionalism. Utilizing path analysis, the results of the study revealed that there is partial mediation on the effect of time management on the relationship between work ethics and professionalism. Moreover, it is significantly pointed out that about 53 percent of the total effect of the time management on the professionalism goes through the mediator variable, work ethics and about 47 percent of the total effect is either or mediated by other variables not included in the model. This implies that work ethics influences time management which in turn influences professionalism.

INTRODUCTION

Professionalism of teachers has been observed globally as one of the central issues in education. The on-going issue focusing on whether teachers' competence have meet professional education standards have continuously hound the universal education institutions. Teachers are expected to demonstrate professionalism in their respective assigned workplace, which comprised of pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence (Shobha, 2020). Contrariwise, in this pandemic time, most of the teachers admitted that they are beseech with numerous problems that hinder them from providing quality teaching performance which is one of the measures of professional competence.

Conversely, laying the foundation of ethical living is vital and at the same time crucial among the teachers as they are responsible for inculcating invaluable life lessons among their students (Hargreaves (2021). Teachers in the global educational institutions play a huge role in student's lives, being considered the greatest influence among the learners they are charged with. To set a positive example, they are expected to exhibit appropriate work ethics as specified in the ethical code of conduct for teachers to guide them in their job and fulfill their objective of providing uncompromising education (Leal Filho, Shiel, Paço, Mifsud, Ávila, Brandli & Caeiro, 2019).

Bridging the gap between work ethics and professionalism is time management skills of teachers (Kennedy-Cullen & Schuette, 2017). Failure of teachers to internalize time management at work redounds to unsatisfactory

work ethics and haphazard work performance (Kashyap, 2021). The common complaint of teachers on not having adequate time, bounces back to lacking time management skills which result in further struggle to meet the deadline in accomplishing and submission of necessary reports. Subsequently, the looming gap brought about by poor time management of teachers results in lack of professionalism, inefficient workflow, and low work ethics. In the Philippines, Republic Act 7836 stipulated the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers which mandated that all public-school teachers are expected to be professionally competent in the practice of their profession (Llego, 2017).

As stipulated in DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, public school teachers are guided by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) a set of standard frameworks that articulated the developmental progression as teachers develop, refine their practice, and respond to the complexities of educational reforms.

In Davao del Sur Division, the superintendent had been staunch in his directive to strengthen the work ethics and professionalism of all teachers and expect teachers to maximize instructional time towards the achievement of learning goals. It has been observed by the superintendency during his rounds of monitoring that there are complaints that several teachers are engaged in personal income-generating activities that adversely affect their work and decrease their instructional time. Moreover, there are also complaints of teachers who come to school late and leave the school premises early in the afternoon which manifest poor time management.

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In this context of heightened emphasis on work ethics and professionalism of teachers, the researcher sought to establish the tenuous link of time management on both variables. This study is considered unique as this specifically tries to scrutinize whether the teachers in Magsaysay North and South District have internalized the construct of quality teaching and teacher quality through the embodiment of work ethics; professionalism; and time management.

Along this point of view, the researcher hopes to make this study a generation of new knowledge that can provide relevant contribution in the field of education. The main thrust of this study was to find out the mediating effect of time management on the relationship between work ethics and professionalism of public school teachers. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To describe the level of work ethics of teachers -in terms of:
 - 1.1 self -management;
 - 2.1 productivity;
 - 2.2 accountability and responsibility,
 - 2.3 instructional competence;
 - 2.4 dedication.
2. To ascertain the level of professionalism of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 pedagogical competence,
 - 2.2 personal competence,
 - 2.3 social competence, and
 - 2.4 professional competence.
3. To measure the level of time management along these indicators:
 - 3.1 time-tracking skill;
 - 3.2 calendaring skill;
 - 3.3 organizational skill; and
 - 3.4 prioritizing skill;
4. To determine the significance of the relationship between work ethics and professionalism, work ethics and time management and time management and professionalism.
5. To determine if the mediating effect of time management on the relationship between work ethics and professionalism.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to provide strong support for the research objectives, which is essential to the manifestation of understanding in the study, a variety of perspectives, theories, findings from research and publications, and insightful observations from various authors relevant to related topics of the study are presented in this section. The independent variable is work ethics with the following indicators: self -management; productivity; accountability and responsibility; instructional competence; and dedication. The dependent variable is professionalism with the following indicators: pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence. The mediating variable is time management with the following indicators: time-tracking

skill; calendaring skill; organizational skill; and prioritizing skill.

Work Ethics

Workplace ethics is described as the set of moral and legal guidelines that are given to employees as guide in attaining institutional objectives (Kusumaningrum, *et al.* 2018). These rules often have an impact on how employees communicate with one another within the company. By purposefully designing ethical guidelines in the organizational structure, employees keep their best interests in mind while maintaining a positive influence on those they impact through their processes (Benedicto & Caelian, 2021).

In the school organization, work ethics of teachers has an immense influence in student's lives, as they are responsible for infusing vital life lessons among their students (Brass & Holloway 2019). To set a positive example, teachers are expected to strictly follow a code of ethical conduct (Brookfield, Rudolph,& Yeo, 2019), to show competence and ensure that these educational guides remain unbiased while doing their tasks and achieve their objective of providing quality education.

According to (Alwaqfi, 2019) the work ethics of teachers comprise purposeful behaviors in a proactive manner to achieve desired level of performance cognizance with the appropriate norms and best practices of the school community. (Bataineh,2020), pointed out that work ethics of teachers are the set of procedures and work routines that are done efficiently and effectively towards the expected instructional standards. (Campbell & Zegwaard,2020) elaborated that the ethical teacher exhibits appropriate moral uprightness, is highly committed to his/her job, transparent in all dealings and possesses a finely-honed sense of judgment.

In the Philippines, the passing of R.A. The Professional Regulation Commission's Board of Professional Teachers adopted Resolution No. 435 s.1997 promulgating and adopting the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers under Republic Act (RA) 7836, also known as the Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994. This is an enhanced version of the Magna Carta Code of Ethics, which outlines expectations and principles for teachers' behavior both within and outside of the classroom. As stated in Section 42 of DepEd Order No. In 2017, the Philippine Professional Standards for Instructors (PPST), a collection of uniform standards that outlined the developmental trajectory as teachers developed, improved their practices, and responded to the complexity of educational reforms, served as a guide for public school teachers (Llego, 2017).

(Goldman, 1970) as cited by (Makamani & Zimanyi, 2020), postulated that work ethics is a set of ethical principles that guide employees in their routinely task by maximizing their official time, prioritizing their jobs and having a strong sense of responsibility towards the accomplishment of institutional goals. The following are used as indicators in the measurement of the work

ethics of the public school teachers: self-management; productivity; accountability and responsibility; instructional competence; and dedication.

Self-management is the first indicator that is mentioned. Self-management, according to (Boreen, 2019), is the capacity to successfully control one's emotions, thoughts, and behaviors in a variety of contexts. This entails controlling stress, inspiring oneself, and establishing and pursuing personal and academic goals. Teachers with strong self-management skills exhibit punctuality in all undertakings, tactful in conversations, courteous and respectful towards others, voluntarily aids team endeavors and willingly extend assistance towards the attainment of organizational goals.

(Brookfield, Rudolph, and Yeo, 2019) viewed self-management as the ability to recognize one's emotions and control the behaviors sparked by those emotions. In the school organization, teachers are expected to demonstrate self-management to manage their commitments and time. They are to cultivate the capability to learn new things to enhance one's work; and build and nurture one's personal development through constant study. Positive attitude is essential for self-management; when teachers embed positive attitude, they are able to take difficult situations as opportunities, take life's obstacles as challenges, take adversities as blessings to learn from; leading to the attainment of personal goals.

The second indicator on work ethics is productivity. (Bataneh, 2020), defined workplace productivity as the efforts extended by employees, and the quality of labor done to achieve the assigned task. In the school organization, this refers to the varied tasks that teachers routinely do such as preparing learning plans; implementing the curriculum; evaluating the learning outcomes; and designing innovations to address learning gaps. In order for teachers to become productive, they are to maximize learning time do their routinely instructional activity, develop appropriate instructional materials to achieve school goals.

According to (Beauchamp & Childress, 2020), productivity among teachers involves the ability to complete instructional tasks and goals. In order to increase efficiency in the workplace, teachers are to get rid of distractions that hamper one's capacity to achieve a task on time. These distractions include constant use of social media such as frequently checking FB posts, Messenger and e-mail messages and digital games. All these are obstacles to teachers' productivity. Hence, focus on the assigned task is vital in the attainment of workplace activity.

The third indicator on work ethics is accountability and responsibility. According to (Evans, Hartman, & Anderson, 2018) teachers who demonstrate a sense of responsibility steadfastly holds oneself accountable for the assigned tasks and can be depended upon in all school undertakings. In the context of teachers, accountability is about answering to varied stakeholders in the school community. Due to the nature of the collaboration

between the school and the community, it is necessary for everyone to answer for their decisions, actions, and omissions. For teachers who are tasked to influence the students' holistic learning, accountability has more specific implications. It is associated with receptiveness and diplomacy in handling feedbacks of the stakeholders, which includes a willingness to explain, defend, and justify actions.

On the other hand, (Mathews, 2019) elucidated that tracing the lines of responsibility and accountability can be difficult. However, responsible teachers willingly accept some degree of accountability for any assigned tasks. Therefore, responsibility could be seen as a collection of duties related to a position or role. Role, when used narrowly, refers to a job description, which in turn includes function but is not restricted to it. Function would be the specifics of the job; therefore, teachers' responsibility would include more than just the primary function of a role. It would also include the various aspects of that function, including the processes, the results, and the effects of the actions taken as part of that collection of duties.

The fourth indicator on work ethics is instructional competence. According to (Alwaqfi, 2019) instructional competence is the hall mark of an effective teacher. Each teacher's primary responsibility is to ensure that they are competent in their instruction, which calls on them to be experts in the subject matter and performance standards that their students should understand. Delivering correct and current knowledge as a teacher requires employing the right methodology, approaches, and strategies. Knowledge of the subject matter and methods for enhancing instruction can be gained through various seminars and training sessions.

As pointed out by (Rane, Narvel, & Bhandarkar, 2019) teachers who exhibit a high degree of instructional competence are continuously motivated to design, innovate and craft relevant instructional materials that are developmentally appropriate for the students. They readily assist their peers in sharing research-based teaching approaches and strategies to enhance the academic outcome of students. An exceptionally competent teacher will do whatever it takes to ensure that the teaching staff works as a team to achieve the learning goals.

The fifth indicator on work ethics is on dedication. (Strayhorn, 2018) postulated that dedication is one of the hallmarks of worker engagement. Every employer wants engaged employees. In the school ambiance, being engaged at work means the teachers maximized instructional time, motivated the students to participate in class discussions, utilized developmentally appropriate strategies to meet the learning objectives.

As described by (Makamani & Zimanyi, 2020), purpose driven, dedicated employees frequently report to the workplace ahead of the others, willingly give assistance and support in all school projects, programs and activities and lead in team endeavors towards the attainment of institutional goals. Teachers who exhibit dedication and

commitment to the job do their tasks because they are driven by the genuine love to accomplish assigned tasks. They constantly feel energized by what they do. They feel they are truly making a difference. They possess positive attitude, model high work ethics and are always productive.

Professionalism

Public education teachers are professionals, as such their role requires both adeptness in curriculum management skills and technical know-how in dealing with varied stakeholders (Bielefeld, 2018). As a professional, it is essential that teachers demonstrate professionalism regularly by being proficient in communication skills. Teachers are to model outstanding communication skills, show tactfulness and diplomacy in all dealings and demonstrate its importance to the students (Garcia, 2020).

The hallmark of professionalism among teachers, according to (Hazan & Musa, 2019), is a steadfast dedication to one's responsibilities as outlined in the teacher code of ethics. Teachers have a significant impact on kids' development, thus they are expected to uphold gender sensitivity in all interactions, foster a climate of civility and respect in the classroom, and convey higher learning objectives for all students. Moreover as elucidated by Guskey (2020), teacher professionalism includes being able to communicate and maintain high standards of learning performance; delivers accurate and updated content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies towards the attainment of improved academic performance of students.

On the other hand, (Zakaria, Nor & Alias, 2021) emphasized that teacher professionalism has been given utmost concern in the global educational institutions, all because they are tasked with the great responsibility of improving the educational performance of students towards the attainment of institutional goals. Effective teaching means being able to address students' learning gaps and ensure that all the competencies in the curriculum are mastered and applied in the students' day to day experiences. A professional teacher is both a reliable role model and an efficient learning facilitator, according to (Seo, 2016), thus they should establish an adequate instructional plan and employ a range of appropriate assessment techniques to track and evaluate student progress toward global competency.

According to (Kramer, 2020), a teacher's competency includes how successfully they carry out their responsibilities as an educator, including how prepared they are for the class. The teachers' instructional competence define their professional performance. Teachers are to maintain a very satisfactory rating when assessed based on the tasks accomplished within an exact period. As pointed out by (Menter and Flores, 2021), teacher professionalism is manifested and exhibited through internal factors such as willingness to work as team member, empathy with the varied types of students, and being purpose driven.

Additionally, institutional factors that are important in teachers' professionalism are being productive in one's responsibilities, duties and functional position; works well towards positive organizational climate; flexible in using instructional approaches and strategies; adept at using online and contextualized learning resources.

(Hurst and Reding, 2020) offered a comparable perspective in which they emphasized the significance of both respect and civility as essential elements of professionalism. Even when it is not reciprocated, a professional respects everyone. A teacher must constantly treat coworkers, parents, and pupils with respect in order to serve as an example of acceptable behavior. Everyone is treated with respect and decency by a professional. Similar to this, (Johnston, 2020) explained how many aspects of communication have an impact on professionalism. Among these are courteous expression in conversation with colleagues and other stakeholders, support, collaboration, cooperation, encouragement, and participation in learning communities are necessary in dealing with others.

Like (Hilferty, 2018) said, professionalism is a process rather than a product. Becoming truly professional is a lifelong challenge, which comprises the way the teachers think about their profession, and how they behave and implement their knowledge and skills related to their profession. Several studies have indicated that the improvement of professionalism encourages teachers to set a higher standard in teaching and learning, towards better instructional performance in the quest for professionalization. In addition, when teachers put numerous efforts in improving their teaching quality, they need an instructional leader, a school head who can motivate them to maximize their instructional time and achieve the institutional goals.

According to (Sachs, 2015), professional instructors are responsible for delivering instruction in the classroom that results in high performance levels of student learning. The use of modern, research-based instructional methodologies, creative techniques and strategies for creating activities for all types of learners, and fostering professional relationships with colleagues all serve as additional examples of teachers' professionalism. According to (Nzulwa, 2019), professionalism is demonstrated by teachers' extensive knowledge of multi-disciplinary integrative modes and techniques of teaching, their in-depth comprehension of the subject area's learning objectives, instructional strategies, and content based on the current curriculum, and their ability to enhance improved academic outcomes.

Professionalism, in the opinion of Brass & Holloway (2019), refers to the traits that distinguish or identify a certain profession or a professional individual. The specific knowledge of professionals is well known. They exhibit a desire to learn more and hone their abilities, and, where necessary, they possess the degrees and certifications that form the basis of this knowledge. According to indicators developed by (Hargreaves, 2017),

teachers are required to have a high degree of flexibility and democratic professionalism, which means that teachers must have a high level of instructional skills and knowledge. The expansion of educational needs necessitates the development of professionalism.

In addition, (Mahulae, Lumbanraja and Siahaan, 2020) elaborated that teachers' attitude of initiative is an important element in professionalism. Teacher-professionals set realistic goals for themselves and their students, and they manifest an attitude of confidence as they indulge in varied instructional initiative to achieve the learning goal. The initiative of teachers gives them the freedom to work independently, enables them to contribute productively with less monitoring, has a continuous improvement strategy to develop competence, and consistently aims to raise the academic standards of pupils.

Similarly, (Mayer, 2016) highlighted the importance of teachers' professionalism as manifested in the decision-making process of selecting curriculum materials and methods of lesson delivery. When the teachers know with certainty that there are identifiable outcomes expected during a prescribed time frame, this provides direction and motivation leading to change. By extending all-out effort with utmost energy and zest, the teachers become exemplary instructional managers. On the other hand, according to (Davidson, 2017), each professional teacher knows the importance of learning outcomes since they represent evidence of change that is taking place inside every classroom. It was further accentuated that professional teachers effectively observe congruence of the lesson objective to the drill, review, lesson proper and the evaluation so as there is continuity until the lesson is done. Along this, teachers engage in careful planning so that there is fluidity in the activities towards institutional success.

(Seifert, 2020) recognized the capacity to be a follower as one fundamental characteristic of professionalism. It's critical for educators to understand their place in the hierarchy. Basically, the attitude of teachers in complying school heads' instruction, offering mutual support, assistance and demonstrating cooperation and following school policies and regulations are marks of a true teacher-professional. Additionally, a teacher's professionalism comes from within. If teachers manifest a positive attitude to their assigned tasks and workload, and carry out their duties wholeheartedly with competence, then they are exhibiting professionalism.

According to (Cavanagh, 2003) as cited by (Wardoyo & Herdiani, 2017) the indicators of teachers' professionalism are: pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and *professional competence*. The first indicator of teachers' professionalism is pedagogical competence. According to (Burlakova, Bogatyreva & Pavlova, 2020) the pedagogical competence of teachers is of vital importance, both for the quality of the educational process and its outcomes. A pedagogically competent teacher is expected to demonstrate an understanding of research-

based knowledge and the principles of teaching and learning. Develop and apply effective teaching strategies to encourage critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills. Model exemplary practice to improve the applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas.

The second indicator of teachers' professionalism is *personal competence*. (Jerez-Jerez, & Melewar, 2020) opined that teachers' personal competence includes qualities required to establish, nurture, and enhance connections with students and their parents, as well as with coworkers and other school community stakeholders. Teachers are expected to demonstrate appropriate appearance and decorum; model the value of punctuality; and being careful about the effect of one's behavior on students. In addition, a teacher is expected to show compassion and flexible in dealing with the students under his/her care. He/ She is to demonstrate a sense of accountability in all assigned task and does things at his/her level best.

The third indicator of teachers' professionalism is *social competence*. (Fauziah, et al., 2020) viewed that teacher are to maintain a learning environment of courtesy and respect; treats others with politeness and diplomacy towards the attainment of harmonious relationship in the assigned school community.

At any time, a teacher attends a conference, association meetings, seminars, or social events, he/she is expected to make sure he/she is able to demonstrate proper decorum and treat others with tact and diplomacy. In dealing with varied stakeholders in the school community, the teachers are to show respect to their multi-cultural background, make appropriate adjustments, exhibit sensitivity and compassion and ensure that collegiality and camaraderie in the workplace is maintained at all times.

The fourth indicator of teachers' professionalism is professional competence. According to (Roth, et al., 2017), professional competence is the comprehensive body of knowledge, disposition, and abilities needed to work in a given field or career. The test of professional competence requires ample disciplinary knowledge and the application of concepts, processes, and skills in the field of work. To improve teaching practices, keep up with educational trends, display an openness to educational trends, communicate, and uphold high standards of instructional performance, teachers must develop professional connections with their peers in the school setting.

Time Management

(Forsyth, 2018), the author of the book on Successful Time Management, identified the elements of time management as follows: time-tracking skill; calendaring skill; organizational skill; and prioritizing skill. All these elements are essential strategies in achieving personal goals. These processes of managing time leads to organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Setting priorities, carrying out plans, and managing time all contribute to creating an environment that is effective in

terms of cost-benefit, quality of output, and time required to complete activities or projects. The practice of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on particular activities, on the other hand, is what (Dierdorff, 2020) characterized as time management. This definition aims to promote effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity. It entails striking a balance between the time constraints imposed by employment, relationships, family, personal interests, and responsibilities with other competing demands. When one manages their time well, they have the freedom to spend or do things at their own pace.

The first indicator of time management is *time-tracking skill*. (Morgenstern, 2020) specified that time tracking enable a person to plan and work more efficiently. This includes mapping out everything that one intends to do, set priorities, and get the goal done on time. Currently, a Project Time Tracking software solution is available in the market. This is essential in project planning. The employee records one's project hours in details and see exactly how much time is spent on each activity. Another component is detailed statistics and reports, this shows reliable and accurate reports where one sees how much time is spent on specific projects and tasks by different units and employees for time frames ranging from one day to one year.

The second indicator of time management is *calendar skill*. According to (LeBoeuf, 2020), in his book Working Smart, calendar skill keeps one organized and productive. With proper calendar management, a person becomes focused and efficient in his/her tasks. Calendar skill comprises planning out, consolidating activities in week, and in the months to come, indicating specific blocks of time, setting aside specific activities. In Creating a master calendar makes scheduling easier, helps one to be more organized, prepared and be more proactive and productive (Schaack, Le, & Stedron, 2020). Organizing one's calendar gets rid of overlapping tasks or meeting and guarantees that one is in the right direction towards the attainment of goals.

The third indicator of time management is *organizational skill*. According to (Ahmad, Batool, and Choudhry, 2019), organizing ability is a crucial tool for completing tasks admirably, effectively, and efficiently. It is an acquired ability that must be mastered and cultivated in order to increase its effectiveness. It is not a natural skill. Employees with outstanding organizational abilities are able to perceive the wider picture, which aids them in successful planning, strategic decision-making, managing teams, setting priorities, and allocating duties in a productive manner to reach institutional goals (Nzewi, Chiekezie, & Ikon, 2016). An essential set of abilities for multitasking is organizational skills. This avoids pointless chaos and procrastination, helps establish structure and order, and facilitates the efficient management of unforeseen delays and problems.

The fourth indicator of time management is *prioritizing skill*. Prioritization is the crucial ability that one needs to

maximize their own and the team's efforts, as explained by (Kennedy-Cullen & Schuette, 2017). In order to direct one's energy and attention on the things that truly matter, one also needs the ability to generate quiet and space in their lives. When one's time is limited and demands seem to have no end, this is crucial. It enables one to allocate their time where it is most needed and most effectively used to complete duties that have been given to them. According to (Walsh's, 2018) hypothesis, effective prioritization and careful management of reprioritized tasks can create order out of chaos, lessen feelings of burnout, and enable successful endeavors. The most popular and logical method of time management is prioritization based on project value.

To summarize the advantages of time management, this leads to improved work practices and higher production. The ability to manage one's time better helps one focus more intently, develop self-control, and accomplish goals. Making good use of one's time enhances happiness and work-life balance. In contrast, effective time management lowers stress, enables one to maximize key tasks and limit distractions, paving the path for a life that is equally balanced between personal and professional responsibilities.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational, quantitative, non-experimental research design. The correlational technique, according to (Creswell, 2018), is a non-experimental design where the researcher explores the link between two or more variables in a natural situation without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, the researcher looks at how changes in one variable were associated with changes in the other variable in order to assess the strength of correlations between variables. A mediation model was also applied in this investigation. A mediation model includes a third explanatory variable, known as a mediator variable, in order to discover and explain the mechanism or process that underlying an observed link between an independent variable (professionalism) and a dependent variable (work ethics) (time management). A mediation model assumes that the independent variable influences the mediator variable, which in turn effects the dependent variable, rather than assuming a direct causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The mediator variable in this study sheds light on how the independent and dependent variables relate to one another. This demonstrates that mediating relationships exist when a third variable plays a significant role in determining how the other two variables interact (Siedlecki, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Work Ethics

Shown in Table 1 is the level of work ethics. The standard deviation was less than 1.00 which means there is consistency of responses among respondents. The overall mean score was 4.08 labelled as high. Distinctively,

the level of work ethics of teachers on the following indicators were as follows: instructional competence, 4.12 described as high; productivity, 4.10, described as

high; dedication, 4.08, described as high; accountability and responsibility, 4.06 described as high; and self-management, 4.05, described as high.

Table 1: Level of Work Ethics

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-Management	0.456	4.05	High
Productivity	0.292	4.10	High
Accountability and responsibility	0.458	4.06	High
Instructional competence	0.351	4.12	High
Dedication	0.475	4.08	High
Overall	0.260	4.08	High

Data implies that the public school teachers have manifested very satisfactory work ethics in terms of self -management; productivity; accountability and responsibility; instructional competence; and dedication. This is indicative that at DepEd the teachers, satisfactorily exhibited responsibility and accountability in working with colleagues and shared opportunities that are differentiated and developmentally appropriate to address the differences in learners’ gender, needs, abilities, interests, and experiences.

Level of professionalism

Shown in Table 2 is the level of professionalism of the respondents. The overall mean score was 3.65 labeled as high. Mainly, the level of professionalism on the following indicators were as follows: personal competence, 3.75, described as high; social competence, 3.63, described as high; pedagogical competence, 3.62 described as high; and professional competence, 3.60, described as high. The data implies that the teachers in the public schools demonstrate very satisfactory level of

Table 2: Level of Professionalism

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Pedagogical competence	0.519	3.62	High
Personal Competence	0.637	3.75	High
Social Competence	0.493	3.63	High
Professional Competence	0.323	3.60	High
Overall	0.270	3.65	High

professionalism on the following indicators: pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence. In line with the insight of (Day *et al.*, 2007), the pedagogical competence of teachers is of vital importance, both for the quality of the educational process and its outcomes. The teachers at DepEd demonstrated acceptable pedagogical competence as a model for exemplary practice to improve the applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas; demonstrate an understanding of research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning; and develop and apply efficient teaching strategies to encourage critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.

teachers in Davao del Sur particularly in Magsaysay South and North District. The overall mean score was 3.67 described as high. This implies that time management is manifested and practiced most of the time. Breakdown of numerical ratings are as follows: organizational skill, 3.79, described as high; calendaring skill 3.78, described as high; prioritizing skill, 3.59, described as high; and time-tracking skill, 3.52, described as high.

The data implies that the teachers showed high level of time management in the following indicators: time-tracking skill; calendaring skill; organizational skill; and prioritizing skill. As posited by (Forsyth, 2013), time management is an essential skill which must be embedded in every person to achieve personal goals. Setting priorities, carrying out plans, and managing time all contribute to creating an environment that is effective in terms of cost-benefit, quality of output, and time required to complete

Level of Time Management

Shown in Table 3 is the level of time management of

Table 3: Level of Time Management

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Time-tracking skill	0.323	3.52	High
Calendaring skill	0.519	3.78	High
Organizational Skill	0.353	3.79	High
Prioritizing Skill	0.359	3.59	High
Overall	0.323	3.67	High

activities or projects. These time management techniques increase the efficacy and efficiency of a company. At DepEd the teachers satisfactorily exhibited this as they mapped out everything that they intend to do, set their priorities, and get their goals done on promptly on time. Conversely, (LeBoeuf, 2001), emphasized the importance of *calendarizing skill*, as this keeps one organized and productive. At DepEd the teachers satisfactorily utilized calendar management, which involved planning out, consolidating activities in week, and in the months to come, indicating specific blocks of time, setting aside specific activities. Through this, scheduling becomes easier, helps them to be more organized, prepared and be more proactive and productive.

Correlations between Work Ethics and Professionalism

Displayed in Table 4 were the results of the test relationship between work ethics and professionalism. Reflected in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at 0.05. The overall r-value is .596 with a p-value of <0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means that there is a significant relationship between work ethics and professionalism. This implies that teachers work ethics is correlated with professionalism. Data reveals that all indicators of work ethics are positively correlated on professionalism, since the p-value is <0.05 than the overall r-value. Data shows the positive association between the two variables.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Work Ethics and Professionalism

Work Ethics	Professionalism				
	Pedagogical Competence	Personal Competence	Social Competence	Professional Competence	Overall
Productivity	.386*(0.000)	.302*(0.000)	.438*(0.000)	.499*(0.000)	.519*(0.000)
Accountability and responsibility	.386*(0.000)	.365*(0.000)	.228*(0.000)	.331*(0.000)	.418*(0.000)
Instructional competence	.421*(0.000)	.416*(0.000)	-.211*(0.000)	.024(0.676)	.204*(0.000)
Dedication	.451*(0.000)	.404*(0.0)	.266*(0.000)	.419*(0.000)	.472*(0.000)
Overall	.475*(0.000)	.386*(0.000)	.496*(0.000)	.570*(0.000)	.596*(0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level*

The findings implied that the teachers collaborated with administrators, fellow teachers and other employees in order to provide a safe and positive learning experience for students. The teacher willingly followed the direction of administrators, to avoid undermining an administrator's authority and to set a positive example for students. In addition, the teachers exhibited exemplary ethical behavior and worked with colleagues as a team in enhancing current practices in the planning and management of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning process.

relationship between work ethics and time management. As indicated in the table, the indicators of work ethics are positively correlated to time management with the overall r-value of .620 with a p-value of <0.05, thus, signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means that there is significant relationship between time management and work ethics. The findings implied that the teachers demonstrated ethical conduct and promptly reported to school, moreover, they observed promptness in submitting reports and maximized official hours in the pursuit of completing an assigned task. Conversely, teachers exhibited satisfactory work ethics displayed adeptness in time management by organizing, prioritizing, scheduling, and calendarizing all pertinent activities towards the attainment of institutional goals.

Correlations between Work Ethics and Time Management

Reflected in Table 5 were the results of the test of

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Work Ethics and Time Management

Work Ethics	Time Management Overall
Productivity	.397*(0.000)
Accountability and responsibility	.463*(0.000)
Instructional competence	.572*(0.000)
Dedication	.605*(0.000)
Overall	.620*(0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level*

Correlations between Time Management and Professionalism

Shown in Table 6 is the data on test of relationship between professionalism and time management. As indicated in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at 0.05 level of significance. In the indicator, *professional*

organization as a major referent, data shows that it is positively correlated with time management. The r-value is .686 with a p-value of <0.05. This shows that professionalism as a major referent is indeed a large part of time management. The overall result reflects that professionalism is positively correlated to time

management having an overall r-value of .670 with a p-value of <0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between professionalism and time management is rejected. The data implied that professionalism and time management are positive traits that are exhibited by the teachers.

They demonstrated a high degree of professionalism, managed one's time satisfactorily, maximized official hours and were prompt in accomplishing reports, projects and other assigned tasks. Similarly exhibited professionalism in all undertakings, showed adeptness in time-tracking; calendaring; organizing; and prioritizing urgent and important tasks.

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Time Management and Professionalism

Time Management	Professionalism				
	Pedagogical Competence	Personal Competence	Social Competence	Professional Competence	Overall
Overall	.686*(0.000)	.626*(0.000)	.319*(0.000)	.448*(0.000)	.670*(0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

On the Mediating Effect of Time Management

Shown in Table 7 is the path analysis on the mediating effect of time management on the relationship between work ethics and professionalism. The data obtained in this table are the results after conducting the SPSS AMOS. This table presents the direct effect of work ethics on time management, time management on professionalism and work ethics on professionalism. Work ethics and time management is the path a coefficient which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .770 standardized regression coefficient of .620, SE of .056 and a probability value less than 0.05. Below the

significance level of 0.05 implies that these two variables have a significant relationship and low or small standard error means that the estimate is more precise. Besides, the effect size or the impact of work ethics on time management is 77% which disavows completely the null hypothesis. Thus, the path b coefficient is time management and professionalism which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .407, standardized regression coefficient of .487, SE of .043 and a p-value less than 0.05 which mean there is a strong conclusion to say that time management and professionalism are significant. The

Table 7: Mediating Effect : Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
WE- TM	.770	.620	.056	13.809	***
TM- PROF	.407	.487	.043	9.480	***
WE- PROF	.306	.294	.053	5.725	***

effect size of time management on professionalism is 41%. And lastly, path c coefficient shows the effect size of work ethics on professionalism. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .306 or 31% efficacy, standardized regression coefficient of .294; the computed standard error is .053 and a p-value of 0.05 which means that work ethics and professionalism are significant. Numerically, this supports the assumption that work ethics is associated with professionalism.

X =WORK ETHICS (WE)
 Y = PROFESSIONALISM (PROF)
 M =TIME MANAGEMENT

In addition, Figure 3 depicts the result of the mediating effect computation. It shows the effect size of path correlation coefficients of the three variables used in this study. At the 0.05 level, the route analysis gave a p value of less than 0.05, which is significant. This suggest that time management has a substantial role in the relationship between work ethics and professionalism among public school teachers. Furthermore, at the conclusion of time management, the mediator variable, the casual association

Figure 3: Regression Weights on The Mediating Effect of Time Management on the Relationship between Work Ethics and Professionalism

between work ethics and professionalism has been lowered from a significant beta coefficient value of .596 to .31, which is still significant. The raw correlation between work ethics and professionalism has a total impact of .596. The extent of the association between work ethics and professionalism with time management included in the regression is represented by the direct effect of .31. The indirect value

of 0.316 represents the amount of original link between work ethics and professionalism that has been transferred to time management. The formula is: $(a*b)$, where “a” is the path between the independent and mediator variables, “b” denotes the path between the mediator and dependent variables.

Divide the indirect effect by the total effect to get the ratio index; in this case, 0.316 divided by .596 equals 0.530. About 53% of the overall influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable appears to be mediated by the mediator variable, while the remaining 47% appears to be either direct or mediated by factors not included in the model. Moreover, there are three steps to be met for a third variable to be acting as mediator (Baron and Kenny, 1986). In Table 7 these are categorized as Steps 1 to 3. Step 4 is the final step. In Step 1 (Path c) work ethics as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicts professionalism, the dependent variable (DV).

In step 2 (Path a) work ethics (IV) significantly predicts time management, the mediator (MV). In step 3 (Path b) time management (MV) significantly predicts professionalism. In like manner, the purpose of steps 1 to 3 is to establish that there are zero-order relationships among variables exist. And we can automatically conclude that mediation is not probable with no relationship variables basing the process of estimating relationship. Furthermore, if there is significant relationship in step 1 to 3, one must proceed to step 4. Then in step 4 the combined effect of work ethics and time management on professionalism is significant.

As a matter of triangulation, further path analysis of mediation effect using AMOS is warranted to assess the significance of the intervening variable. Additionally, full mediation will be accomplished if the effect of the IV on the DV ceases to be significant at the conclusion of the analysis. This indicates that the mediating variable is a mediator of all effects. Only partial mediation is accomplished if the regression coefficient is significantly decreased but still significant at the last stage. This indicates that the MV mediates a portion of the IV. In this instance, reducing MV greatly reduces the impact of the IV (work ethics) on DV (professionalism) (time management). Therefore, while the effect is still large, only partial mediation occurred.

The researcher demonstrated that mediation is significant and that there is partial mediation using Baron and Kenny’s steps in testing mediation of time management. First, perform a straightforward regression analysis to test for path a, the independent variable, with X predicting M. or X (work ethics) affects the mediator or M (time management) at beta coefficient of .77 with a SE of .07 and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. Second, conduct a simple regression analysis with M predicting Y to test for the significance of path b- the mediating variable or M (time management) affects the dependent variable or D (professionalism) at beta coefficient of .41, where time management got a residual error of .06 and the relationship is significant at 0.05

significance level.

Third, conduct a simple regression analysis with X predicting Y to test for the significance of path c- the independent variable or X (work ethics) affects the dependent variable or Y (professionalism) at beta coefficient of .31, where professionalism has a residual error of .04 and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. As a learning insight, the researcher concurred the importance of time management in effecting work ethics and professionalism in the workplace. These are positive traits that must be embedded in the hearts of all teachers. A teacher who demonstrates a high degree of professionalism, acts with ethical conduct and manages one’s time properly by maximizing instructional time and being prompt in accomplishing assigned tasks, towards the attainment of institutional goals.

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